

Fig S7. Discrete set of points (yellow) segmented from a noisy fluorescence image **(A)**. By using Gaussian process regression with varying parameters of the underlying Poisson kernel, different estimations of the membrane can be obtained. The curvature of these estimated contours are shown in **(B)**. The parameters were chosen as follows: $r=0.4$ (blue), $r=0.65$ (green), and $r=0.9$ (red). In **(C, $r=0.4$)**, the resulting contour is highly underfitted which leads to a strongly regularized curvature. In **(E, $r=0.9$)**, an overfitting effect can be observed, resulting in high fluctuations of the curvature. In **(D, $r=0.65$)** a more plausible parameter was chosen leading to an accurate approximation while preserving the main characteristics of the curvature. The corresponding local motion kymographs are shown in panel **(F – H)**. For **(F, $r=0.4$)**, some details are not resolved. In contrast, only few differences can be observed between **(G, $r=0.65$)** and **(H, $r=0.9$)**, which shows that the estimate for $r=0.65$ is already an accurate approximation of the contour.